

**THEORETICAL AND BASIC ISSUES OF ORGANIZING INTERNATIONAL
FESTIVALS****Nurullayeva Zarina**The Uzbekistan State Institute of Arts and Culture Student of the department
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Abstract: This text describes the socio-cultural nature of festivals, their global and national importance, and the role of Uzbekistan's international festivals in promoting the national heritage. In addition to world-famous holidays, the article analyzes the organizational and financial mechanisms and artistic features of the "Boysun Spring" and "Silk and Spices" festivals under the auspices of UNESCO. Also, the reforms implemented in the years of independence in the historical cities of Samarkand, Navoi, Bukhara in terms of development of handicrafts (paper-making, goldsmithing, carpet-making, pottery) and tourism, as well as ensuring the employment of women were considered. The international recognition, export potential and prospects of digitization of the industry of Uzbekistan's music, cinematography, dance ("Lazgi") and Rishton, Gijduvan pottery schools are revealed on a scientific and analytical basis.

Key words: International festival, Boysun spring, UNESCO, cultural heritage, folklore, folk art, Samarkand paper, silk and spices, Uzbek pottery, Rishton ceramics, development of tourism, cultural exchange.

Festival (Latin: *festivus* - joyful), a public holiday consisting of a collection of achievements in music, theater, film, variety, and circus arts. It first appeared in Great Britain at the beginning of the 18th century. Since the 20th century, it has been widely used among peoples. Festivals can be national or international.

In the early years of civilization, people invented various rituals as a way to "appease" Mother Nature. Religions and beliefs have changed and expanded over time. Today, the world is a global village, and people, regardless of religion, caste, and nationality, celebrate together by holding ceremonies and events. Today we will get acquainted with beautiful festivals that please the eyes and give a special inspiration to a person.

"Alvon Sails" White Nights Festival, Russia - The "White Nights" international art festival is celebrated in the Arctic Circle in St. Petersburg. The main attraction of the festival is that in the middle of the firework show, a red "Alvon Sails" ship will appear in the water, illuminated with amazing lights. Along with entertainment and songs, the graduates will go on a trip along the Neva, symbolizing their freedom from school and its rules. This tradition started after the Second World War and is held every summer.

Winter Illumination Festival, Japan - The Winter Illumination Festival is held in Kuwana, home to Nabano No Sato Park, which features greenhouses, gardens, and a special light tunnel during the winter season, along with many other festivals throughout Japan from November to March. During the day, millions of solar-powered LED lights all light up at the same time to create stunning scenes, while sparks sparkle over land and water, creating powerful themed images and landscapes, transforming the garden into a fairytale wonderland.

International Balloon Festival, USA - Hundreds of decorated balloons of all shapes, sizes and colors fill the sky for nine days at this spectacular annual festival. Fixed balloons illuminated by propane burners reflect a very beautiful scene. It all started in 1972 with the opening celebration of radio station 770 KKOB in Albuquerque. Today, this festival has become the biggest and most beautiful balloon festival in the world.

Holi, Indian peoples - India is a place of colors and one of the most beautiful holidays - Holi - was born here. People celebrate by sprinkling powdered paints called Gulal, Aabir on each other. It perfectly matches the mood of the spring season, the season of love and colors. The celebration of the death of the evil spirit Holika by lighting a bonfire is an important part of the holiday. Generally, people enjoy life during the glorious Holi in the splendor of colors and expressing their love for each other.

There are many other great festivals celebrated around the world. Lavish and beautiful holidays are a reflection of inner peace and happiness achieved as a result of such celebrations. To experience the true spirit of the holidays, the best way to celebrate them is to come together with an open mind, bypassing all religious or racial boundaries or restrictions.

Boysun Spring is an international open folklore festival traditionally held in April-May in the village of Padang, Boysun District, Surkhandarya Region, Uzbekistan. This festival is under the auspices of UNESCO. In 2001, the Boisun culture was recognized by UNESCO as a masterpiece of oral and intangible cultural heritage of mankind. Boysun was selected among the objects of cultural heritage of the world community in 19 nominations. In 2008, it was included in UNESCO's Representative List of Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity.

For the first time, in May 2002, the first open folklore festival of folk performers of Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan was held. The festival, which attracted the attention of not only Uzbeks, but also foreigners, stopped due to some reasons in 2005 and was not held for 11 years. But since 2016, it has been re-transferred. During the pandemic period, i.e. between 2020-2021, the replay was suspended. Starting from 2022, it will be organized every two years.

Boisun is a simple town located at the foot of Boisuntog mountains. Its main feature is that the local population has preserved ancient customs and traditions that have lasted for more than a thousand years and originated from pagan culture before Islam. A thousand years ago, poets created the heroic epic "Alpamish" here. Boysun also has its own musical culture, characterized by many rituals, music and dance.

Festival process. More than 200 representatives of folklore groups operating in different regions of Uzbekistan will participate in the festival with costumes and ancient songs typical of their regions. During its organization, more than 100 huts will be built and mounds will be erected in the village of Padang. A separate place for wrestling will be prepared and judges from the Republic will be invited. In addition, a national wrestling competition, ethnospports, bicycle marathon, goat-pulling, varrak throwing, rope pulling, chillak, cockfighting and other folk games will be held. Representatives of foreign countries can also participate in the festival, which will be held in the nominations of folklore art - alla, olan, lapar, dance, terma, ritual songs and national folk games, performing arts. A vivid example of this is the arrival of craftsmen from Tajikistan and Afghanistan in 2022. At the end of the festival, the best folklore-ethnographic and best hut-building teams, winners of sports and folk games will be awarded. The regulations on the composition of the organizing committee for the preparation of the international folklore festival "Boysun Bakhori" and the procedure for its holding were approved. It sets out the conditions for holding the festival, including the requirements for the performance of a program by folklore teams of no more than 12 people in the direction of folk applied arts and no more than 4 people in the direction of national games and performances. Also, the criteria for evaluating the festival participants on a 10-point system by a jury of 9-11 leading experts and the procedure for determining the winners were determined.

The costs associated with the organization and holding of the festival are formed on the basis of an estimate developed by the Surkhandarya regional administration and the Ministry of Culture: 30 percent - from funds allocated from the republican budget to the Ministry of Culture for holding cultural events; 70 percent - from additional sources of the local budget of Surkhandarya region, as well as donations from individuals and legal entities, and other sources not prohibited by law. Scientific and practical conferences have been organized within the framework of this festival for several years. Scientists from China, the Czech Republic, South Korea, Kazakhstan, Japan, Russia, France and a number of other countries participated in them. Scientists and craftsmen participating in scientific conferences and forums identified about 50 monuments. In addition, during an international expedition sponsored by UNESCO, about 100 examples of performing arts - epics, lapars and folk songs - were recorded by art historians. The world's largest sozana was sewn for the 2024 open folklore festival "Boysun Spring". The sozana, sewn by craftsmen from Boysun, is 31 meters long and 5.2 meters wide. Also, the festival, which traditionally takes place every two years for two days, lasted a week this year. Special decorations were made in the "Bibishirin" neighborhood for the festival.

The goal was to familiarize guests from other countries with the cultural life, lifestyle and national values of the oasis residents.

The organizers of the festival are UNESCO. The Ministry of Culture and Tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Khokimiyat of Surkhandarya region.

In order to attract many tourists to the republic and familiarize them with the history of our homeland, a number of tasks were carried out during the years of independence. For example, a number of additional events were held in order to attract more foreign tourists to the city of Samarkand.

The craftsman Z. Mukhtorov, who fully mastered the secrets of making ancient Samarkand paper, founded the "Konigil-Meros" papermaking craft center in 1995 in the part of the "Konigil" village where the Siyob River flows, with the support of Uzbekistan, UNESCO and the Japanese International Agency for International Cooperation (JEICA). In 2006, at the initiative of the "El Holding" scientific and production association operating in Samarkand, the "El Merosi" historical costume theater was established. The activities of this theater and craft center play an important role in providing tourists visiting Samarkand with valuable information about the culture and history of the city. In the Koltosin mahalla of the Payarik district, carpets are still woven in several types, directions and methods from wool, silk, hemp, cotton and other threads. Nowadays, it is customary to weave embroidered and printed carpets in Payariq, adapting them to the size of the rooms.

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In the Navoi region, Hadicha Vohidova managed to open a private firm “Khadicha” in Bostan. The firm launched the production of more than 20 types of products based on the Bukhara style of goldsmithing. In accordance with the resolution of the Samarkand city governor No. 214 dated February 2, 2010, a two-story building located on Tashkent Street in the city was completely renovated and the “Samarkand Craftsmen Center” was established here. In 2009-2010, at the initiative of the Samarkand region governor, all the shops located on Tashkent Street were demolished and modern stalls were built in their place. At the same time, shops selling 11 types of folk arts and crafts, such as musical instruments, jewelry, sewing, goldsmithing, and embroidery, have been launched at these stalls. Naturally, these have clearly demonstrated their importance in developing tourism and supporting women's labor. Conditions have also been created to provide women with funds to support their work at home. For example, in 2011, Muhabbat Rahimova, who received a preferential 10 million loan from the "Mikrokredit" bank, opened a private enterprise called "Chuya Marvaridi", equipped it with sewing machines, and employed 8 college graduates. In a private enterprise, in 2012, 8 million soums worth of student uniforms were sewn for the Chuya College of Economics alone. On May 25-27, 2018, the XVII International Silk and Spices Festival was held in Bukhara. The Silk and Spices Festival was held in cooperation with the Hunarmand Association, the State Committee for Tourism Development, and the Bukhara Regional Administration. This festival serves to preserve the cultural heritage of the Uzbek people. The main goal of the festival was to develop national crafts and national economic achievements on an international scale, expand cultural ties, and turn Bukhara into one of the world tourism centers. The program of the XVII International Silk and Spices Festival included performances by national ensembles and an international exhibition of silk products and spices manufacturers from all over the country. At the same time, an exhibition and trade of national handicraft products was organized by more than 100 domestic and foreign craftsmen. In addition, various master classes, national games and entertainment, an exhibition of the fine and applied arts gallery were held. Films dedicated to the history of Uzbekistan were also shown as part of the festival. On February 2-8, 2019, the State Museum of the History of Applied Arts and Crafts of Uzbekistan organized an exhibition and a scientific and practical seminar entitled "Lifelong Jewelry", dedicated to January 31 - "International Jewelry Day", which included the most unique works of the museum's jewelry collection of 2019.

The art of Uzbekistan has a rich and diverse cultural heritage, which occupies a special place in the international arena. International festivals play an important role in cultural exchange and global recognition of art. At the same time, these festivals act as a means of bringing national art to a new level. For the successful promotion of Uzbek art in the international arena, the constant efforts of artists, their exchange of experience and international cooperation are of decisive importance. Various areas of art, including musical performance, applied art, film and theater art, are attracting a lot of attention through international festivals. In particular, Eastern music, national dance and handicraft products have become a unique brand in the international arena. Also, international festivals serve not only as a space for artists to exchange experience, but also as a platform for starting new cultural and creative projects. As a result of these processes, the art of Uzbekistan not only preserves a rich cultural heritage, but also enriches it with modern innovative approaches and is recognized worldwide.

The success of Uzbekistan in international festivals creates an important foundation for the development of national art. These successes not only increase the creative potential, but also play a big role in strengthening the image of Uzbekistan in the international cultural arena. For example:

1. "Sharq Taronalari" festival: This festival became an important platform for the international recognition of the music of Uzbekistan. At the 2019 festival, performers of national musical instruments took high places and made a great impression on the international musical community.

2. Achievements of cinematography: Uzbek films have successfully participated in international film festivals in recent years. For example, the film "To'maris" won an award at the 2020 "Global Film Awards" festival. Such successes demonstrate the capabilities of the national film industry on a global scale.

3. Practical arts and crafts: Uzbek artisans participate in international exhibitions and fairs and make a great contribution to the promotion of national culture. For example, at the "Crafts of the World" festival organized in 2022, masters from Samarkand won the gold medal in the international competition.

Dance art: National dance ensembles take an active part in international festivals and convey the rich traditions of the dance culture of Uzbekistan to the world public. In particular, it is worth noting that the "Lazgi" dance, performed as part of the "Days of Dance and Culture" festival, is included in the list of intangible cultural heritage of UNESCO.

The results show that participation in international festivals serves not only the recognition of national art in the world, but also the opening of new opportunities for artists. At the same time, through such events, international cultural cooperation is further strengthened, and an integral connection between national and international culture is being formed. His achievements in various art fields were highly appreciated at international festivals and competitions.

In researching the place of Uzbek art in the international arena, a wide range of literature and studies were studied. In particular, articles published in national and foreign publications, reports of UNESCO and other international organizations, as well as statistical data on the results of the festival were taken as a basis. In his work "Art and Culture of Uzbekistan", Karimov highlighted the successes of national art in the international arena and paid close attention to the processes of recognition of these achievements on a global scale. Also, Kadyrov's book "Achievement of Uzbek art at international festivals" shows the main trends in the development of national art. This work includes a detailed analysis of the role of international festivals in the successful promotion of national art on a global scale. At the same time, UNESCO reports are important among foreign sources.

Education and exchange of experience in the field of ceramics will also be of great importance in the future. The preservation and development of national art will be ensured by organizing special programs and courses for the new generation of potters. At the same time, international festivals and exhibitions held in Uzbekistan will be organized on a larger scale in the future, which, in turn, may play an important role in promoting the national art of ceramics to the whole world. It is possible that the art of ceramics, which is the cultural heritage of Uzbekistan, will be recognized not only nationally, but also globally and will become an integral part of the international market in the future. Therefore, supporting this industry, training a new generation of potters and promoting them internationally is of strategic importance for the culture and economy of Uzbekistan. Traditional crafts and arts of Uzbekistan are being integrated into the modern world through digital platforms, innovative stage technologies and international festivals. This process

serves to improve the state economy and the spirituality of society, while preserving national values.

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